

THE IMPACT OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT ON THE FUNCTION OF EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE APPRAISALS IN INDUSTRIAL COMPANIES-CASE STUDYS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed at identifying the impact of knowledge management on the function of employee performance appraisals (it is one of the most important functions of human resources management) in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies, relying on the descriptive analytical approach. A questionnaire has been developed and distributed on individuals of the study sample consisting of managers of departments and sections of human resources in each company. The number of questionnaire retrieved and valid for statistical analysis (294) representing (86.5%) of the distributed questionnaires. In order to analyze the study sample, reliance was placed on descriptive statistics, represented in the arithmetic means and standard deviations, in addition to the multiple linear regression analysis in hypothesis testing. The study reached a number of findings, most importantly, the presence of statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$) for the knowledge management including its dimensions (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, knowledge application) on the function of employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies. The study has recommended that the Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies should follow an efficient evaluation system capable of identifying the employees' weaknesses.

KEYWORDS

Human resources management, Knowledge Management, Employee Performance Appraisals, Industrial Companies

1. INTRODUCTION

Business organizations have witnessed many rapid and successive events and developments represented in the technological advancement, more intensive competition [2] and the transformation towards knowledge economy. Such economy has made knowledge as lifeblood of organizations and a backbone to conduct their various work and activities, as a basic element of success and maintenance of their identity, existence; in addition to enhance their capacity to achieve superiority, creativity, and reach their goals. Such important role of knowledge in the organization along with its impact on its activities and work has been a motive in order to move towards knowledge management as a method aiming at keeping up with events and changes, and achieving efficient use of intangible resources, in order to serve its goals and help in change and develop. Therefore, it contributes to the success, progress and prosperity of organizations.

The transformation towards knowledge economy had the largest impact on human resources management and its functions in organizations. Such transformation has resulted in the emergence of reorientation of organizations towards the focus on personnel management, represented in the: attraction, recruitment, compensations payment, promotions granting and sanction imposing, training, layoff, and termination of service for they secure individuals physiological, economic and social needs. In such a way that guarantees compatibility between individual needs and organization goals. Thus, helping in providing a working environment that stimulates individuals and drive them towards the development and exploitation of their knowledge, skills and capabilities to achieve competitive advantages; consequently, contributing to the superiority and advancement of organizations.

Industrial companies are considered among the most prominent business organizations that rely in conducting their activities and functions on knowledge, especially that stored in the human mind, or acquired in individual working in it to achieve their goals. Since the knowledge they have influence their recognition of the nature of activities and operations they do, and duties they perform. It is also considered as a key to solve problems and obstacles they face in work.

Hence, the purpose of this study is to recognize the impact of knowledge management on the function of employee performance appraisals in shareholding industrial companies.

PROBLEM AND ELEMENTS OF THE STUDY

Getting access to knowledge-based economy has increased the value and importance of human resources for mental and intellectual contents of the latter and asone source of knowledge, information, suggestions, and innovations. It is also considered among the most important assets of an organization without which it does not exist, and which affect the productivity of the work. It represents one basic approach in achieving its goals. Thus, it was important to invest and use its intellectual and mental capabilities and contents to achieve goals and mission of the organization.

Despite what has been demonstrated bythe study of [15] that organizations recognizes the importance of knowledge, and its management and role in achievingthe goals of the organization, taking advantage of this knowledge didnt reach the desired level. The result is due to the limited vision ofhuman resources, and the absence of methods and strategies, which increase the interest and focus on it, that might result from the weakness in the effective organizational structure of the organization, in addition to the changing working environment. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to measure the impact of knowledge management on the function of employee performance appraisals.

To achieve the purpose of the study, the following question will be answered:

Is there an impact for the knowledge management including its dimensions (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application) on the function of human resources management (performance appraisal) in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study mainly seeks to search the impact of knowledge management including its dimensions (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application) on the function of human resources management (performance appraisal) in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies. From this purpose, the next sub-purposes have emerged:

Search the impact of knowledge management on employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

This study is based on the following null hypothesis:

Main hypothesis H₀: there is no statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$) for the knowledge management including its dimensions (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application) on the function of employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies.

MODEL OF THE STUDY

In order to achieve the purpose of the study and reach its goals (identifying the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable including its dimensions) the researchers prepared a model especially for this study based on the previous studies. Figure 1 shows the model of the study and its dimensions, as well as the relations between these variables.

Figure (1): Model of the Study

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

The study has aspects of importance:

Firstly: Theoretical Importance

The study has theoretical importance for it is searching for knowledge management and its dimensions (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application) as a concept related to the organizations keeping up with the requirements of knowledge and knowledge economy, and connecting them with the function of employee performance appraisals in organizations. The theoretical importance of the study is also illustrated in its addressing one of the most influential sectors in economy of the country and one of the most dependent on its tacit knowledge in presenting its products.

Secondly: Applied Importance

The dimensions of knowledge management including; knowledge generation, storage, sharing and application, by employees, are connected with the implicit and explicit knowledge acquired by them, which by turn affect their understanding of the operations they do and duties and obligations they perform and increase their ability to solve emerging problems and suggest solutions. Given that industrial firms heavily rely on this knowledge, according to the nature and type of work it perform. Consequently, the integration between knowledge management with what employees have as a reflection for what has done by human resources management in the function of employee performance appraisals. This study is of benefit to the administration of industrial public shareholding companies to know the extent to which the dimensions of knowledge management influence the function of employee performance appraisals.

2. A GENERAL OVERVIEW OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

Knowledge management is one of the modern administrative concepts, given that in the late twentieth century, and with the spread of globalization and the high intensive inter-firms competition, administrations of firms started to exploit internal and external knowledge to achieve superiority and success for their organizations. The concentration was shifted from the attention on information technology to the concentration on how to access to knowledge, merge individuals of organizations in such knowledge, use it in the best possible way, by dealing and then applying it on the ground, and share this knowledge between the organization and individuals [1].

TYPES AND SPECIFICATIONS OF KNOWLEDGE

There are many opinions and classifications, which determine the types of knowledge, among these is that knowledge can be divided into four types [12]:

The first type: Explicit knowledge, it is known as a knowledge that can be expressed, by words or actions, accessed, exploited and shared through books, meeting and seminars... etc.

The second type: Implicit knowledge, it is explained as the knowledge that has been stored in individual's mind and can be accessed through question or discussion. It can be achieved through experiments, experiences and personal judgment.

The third type: Tacit knowledge, it is similar to the implicit knowledge in terms of where it exists, but it is difficult to access, as this happens through conclusions and behavior follow-up.

The fourth type: Unknown knowledge, which means the knowledge, which is discovered through experience and research.

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Knowledge can be represented in three dimensions [11]:

Technological dimension: such as: search engines, electronic systems and databases concerning knowledge management that help in dealing with operations of knowledge management.

Organizational and logistic dimension of knowledge: this dimension reflects the mechanism through which knowledge is obtained, managed and developed. The use of possible ways to achieve the maximum benefit from the use of knowledge is included under this dimension.

Social dimension: this dimension is related to the sharing of knowledge, mechanisms of this sharing and the way of knowledge diffusion among society members. This society is concerned with the society of organization, institution or the society in its external form.

DEFINITION OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

Knowledge management is defined as the transformation of implicit knowledge into explicit knowledge and sharing it within the organization. It is also the process through which values from intellectual assets are generated [17]. Table 1 summarizes the definition of knowledge management regarding the related dimensions:

Findings Dimension	right knowledge in the appropriate place, at the appropriate time, in the right form
Operations Dimension	organized management of the operation, through which knowledge is defined, created, shared and applied
Technological Dimension	it is the total of business intelligence, research and intelligence operations

Table (1): definition of knowledge as perceived by Benjamins
Source [17]

OPERATIONS OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

The definition of knowledge management is connected with the operations of knowledge that manages it. Generally, it works on transforming implicit knowledge into explicit knowledge that can be recovered and analyzed. As in many topics of knowledge management, researchers and scholars of such topics did not completely agree on the identification of knowledge management, but through studies and researches reviewed by the researchers, it was found that there is an agreement on a set of basic operations in knowledge life cycle. In the following table, I introduce some perspectives concerning these operations:

Table (2) Processes of Knowledge Management

Nickols as in [13]	Bukowitz & Williams as in [9]	Wiig as in [18]	Rollett as in [14]	Altaweel and Rasheed as in [6]	Darwazeh as in [10]	Al-kbaisi as in [3]
Knowledge acquisition	Knowledge achieving	Knowledge creation	Knowledge planning	Knowledge identification	Knowledge identification	Knowledge generation
Knowledge organization	Knowledge utilization	Knowledge supply	Knowledge creation	Defining knowledge goals	Knowledge generation	Knowledge storage
Knowledge allocation	Knowledge learning	Knowledge classification	Knowledge merging	Knowledge generation	Knowledge storage	Knowledge distribution
Knowledge storage	Contributing to knowledge	Knowledge transformation	Knowledge organization	Knowledge storage	Knowledge distribution	Knowledge application
Knowledge recovery	Knowledge evaluation	Knowledge dissemination	Knowledge transfer	Knowledge distribution	Knowledge application	
Knowledge distribution	Knowledge building	Knowledge application	Knowledge retention	Knowledge application		
Knowledge retention	Knowledge refinement	Achieving the value of knowledge	Knowledge evaluation			
Knowledge refinement						

(Source: the researchers based on the references mentioned in the table)

As we can notice from the previous table, it is clear that the majority of researches agree on that processes of knowledge management go through basic stages, in different names, and these are:

Firstly: Knowledge Generation

It is the first stage of knowledge management operations. It is the product of data and information held by the organization. As demonstrated by [8], it could be obtained through (knowledge purchasing, conclusion, production, creation and acquisition). In addition, there are basic principles of knowledge creation represented in the reinforcement of individual's capabilities and pushing them to share knowledge and achieve institutionalization in organizations [3].

Secondly: Knowledge Storage

It means the retention of knowledge within the organization aiming at recovering and utilizing it by employees [7]. This process aims to gather knowledge in stores containing details necessary by its users in such a way that increase their knowledge and support its investment by the organization through tools that guarantee its access such as, notes, reports, proposals and essays. All of these can be computerized in order to facilitate its storage and recovery in a form of databases [19].

Thirdly: Knowledge Sharing

Which means that the process of knowledge transfer and exchange among individuals, through a set of operations, to be a base in generating new knowledge as an outcome of the processes of exchange and share.

This means utilizing the appropriate knowledge at the appropriate time and through the appropriate individuals and means. This can be achieved through the process of sharing knowledge or by its separate application. Knowledge, irrespective of its nature, has no benefit unless it is applied in practice, then it becomes of human and civilizational value [4]. These operations can be described in the following figure.

Figure (2): Knowledge Management Processes
(Source: The researchers based on the references mentioned in table (2))

PERFORMANCE APPRAISALS

The process of performance appraisal is a main axis in functions of human resources of an organization, through which you can identify the employee's level of competence in works assigned to him by recognizing strengths and weaknesses in individual and measuring employee performance standards using standards within the organization. Al-Salem and Saleh [5] define it as a periodic process aims at measuring strengths and weaknesses in the individual's effort. According to [20], the effective periodic appraisal of employees performance level in the organization and comparing this appraisal with the tasks linked to them, help decision makers in identifying strengths and weaknesses regarding each individual activity in the organization aiming at addressing the weaknesses and reinforcing the strengths in individuals. Individual accomplishments, in the future, can also be predicted through it.

2. METHOD AND PROCEDURES

This part describes the study methodology adopted by the researchers. It also contains the study community, as well as, how to identify the specified sample. It clarifies the steps of preparing and

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developing the study tool, procedures, through which the study was carried out and statistical methods used in data processing and drawing conclusions.

TYPE AND NATURE OF THE STUDY

The researchers used, in designing the study, the following strategies

Firstly: the theoretical framework that aims to identify concepts concerning knowledge management processes, as well as the function of employee performance appraisals.

Secondly: the analytical part in order to recognize the impact of knowledge management on the function of employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies, through data gathered from the study population through the questionnaire prepared for this purpose.

Thirdly: data analysis through the statistical program -Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)- using suitable statistical methods to describe properties of the study sample, answer the questions of the study and testing hypotheses to arrive at conclusions and recommendations.

Finally: the researchers relied on the sampling strategy, where a sample of the targeted population was taken to utilize it in the data needed for the study.

STUDY POPULATION

The study community consisted of all managers working in public shareholding companies listed in Amman Stock Exchange until the end of 2015, which reached (243) company distributed over the three industrial sectors: the financial sector (111 companies), the service sector (59 companies) and the industrial sector (73 companies). Department and sections managers concerned with human resources in each company have been targeted. Therefore, the total number of the population individuals estimated at (2916) managers.

STUDY SAMPLE

The researchers relied on the proportionate stratified random sample to pull a sample from shareholding companies. With reliance on Sekaran Statistical tables, to determine the sample size [16], (340) questionnaires were distributed; of which (318) were retrieved, but (24) questionnaires were excluded because they were incomplete. Thus, the number of the returned and valid questionnaire was (294) with a retrieval rate of (86.5%) of the distributed questionnaires.

The questionnaire consisted of three parts; the first part concluded the demographic variables and the second part contained the independent variable “knowledge management processes”, whereas the third part included the dependent variable “employees performance appraisal function” in order to gather primary data from employees in public shareholding companies.

To answer the questions of the study and identify the approval degree of the different items of the model, the researchers relied on Likert quintuple scale to measure the response of the study sample individuals. This formula of Likert quintuple scale has been previously adopted by many foreign and Arabic studies, which specialized in impact revealing.

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 Responses of the study sample were calculated which provided the following weights (Strongly agree=5, agree=4, neutral=3, disagree=2, strongly disagree=1)

TOOL OF THE STUDY

To achieve the goals of the study, the questionnaire was developed utilizing the previous studies, thesis, and scientific researches, in addition to consult specialists in this topic. The questionnaire contains the following parts:

The first part: measures the demographic variables (gender, age, educational qualification, nature of work and years of experience).

The second part: measures the independent variables represented in knowledge management processes.

The third part: measures the dependent variable represented in the employees performance assessment.

3. DATA ANALYSIS AND HYPOTHESES TESTING

This part of the study describes and analyzes the study data and provides a description for the characteristics of the study sample and its variables, in addition to the relative importance of the study items. Then an analysis of the responses to the study questions, testing hypotheses and providing comments.

DESCRIBING CHARACTERISTICS OF THE STUDY SAMPLE

This part describes the defining and demographic characteristics of study sample individuals: (gender, age, educational qualification, nature of work and years of experience). For the purpose of describing the study sample, frequencies and percentages of demographic variables of individuals of the study sample were calculated as follows:

Firstly: Gender

Table (3): distribution of sample individuals according to the gender variable

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	159	54.1
	Female	135	45.9
	Total	294	100

As shown in table (3), males represent about (54.1%) of the study sample, while females represent about (45.9%) of the sample indicating the convergence between the two genders. It also demonstrates impartiality of Shareholding Company's management in the selection and recruitment processes

Secondly: Age

Table (4): distribution of sample individuals according to the age variable

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	20 to less than 30 years	44	15.0
	30 to less than 40 years	95	32.3
	40 to less than 50 years	91	31.0
	50 years and older	64	21.8
	Total	294	100

As shown in table (4) age category (20 to less than 30 years) is the smallest category representing about (15%), while age category (30 to less than 40 years) is the largest representing about (32.3%) followed by the category (40 to less than 50 years). This indicates that individuals of administrative staff in shareholding companies are concentrated in the youth category; where reaching administrative positions needs enough time to make sure that qualified personnel are in the right administrative position.

Thirdly: Educational Qualification

Table (5): distribution of sample individuals according to the educational qualification Variable

Variable	Category	Frequency	percentage
Educational qualification	Less than bachelor's degree	18	6.1
	Bachelor's degree	210	71.4
	Master's degree	47	16.0
	PhD	19	6.5
	Total	294	100

As shown in table (5) (bachelor's degree) holder constitute the largest percentage amounted to (71.4%) in conformity with the general orientation concerning the recruitment of bachelor degree holders as a minimum qualification.

Fourthly: Nature of Work

Table (6): distribution of sample individuals according to the nature of work

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Nature of work	Board member	9	3.1
	Director general	12	4.1
	Deputy director general	23	7.8
	Director of the unit	84	28.6
	Head of department	166	56.5
	Total	294	100

As shown in table (6) the category (Board member) represented the smallest percentage (3.1%), while the category (Head of department) represented the largest percentage (56.5%) in conformity with the administrative hierarchy in public shareholding companies, where the number increases as we move towards to the base of the pyramid.

Fifthly: Years of Experience

Table (7): distribution of sample individuals according to years of experience,

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Years of experience	Less than 5 years	23	7.8
	5- less than 10 years	92	31.3
	10 – less than 15 years	114	38.8
	15 years and older	65	22.1
	Total	294	100

As shown in table (7) study individuals are characterized by having relatively high practical experience. The experience category (Less than 5 years) represents the smallest percentage (7.8%), while the percentage of the rest of categories was higher. This indicates that public shareholding companies maintain high-level experiences.

ANALYSIS OF STUDY QUESTION

This part describes variables of the study and items of the questionnaire. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of items were calculated to judge the approval degree and identify the relative importance at each item. The results were as follows:

Knowledge Management Processes, including

KNOWLEDGE GENERATION

Table (8): means, standard deviations and relative importance of knowledge generation items

No.	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Relative importance
1	The company makes sure to attract new knowledge through various means	4.653	0.754	1	high
2	The company motivate employees to innovate in order to produce new knowledge	4.646	0.751	2	high
3	The company pay attention to previous experiences in several processes to generate new knowledge	4.279	1.020	4	high
4	The company provides different mechanisms and ways to give employees the opportunity to acquire new knowledge	4.378	0.741	3	high
5	The company has a budget to support knowledge generation processes (purchasing, creation, conclusion, acquisition)	4.184	0.822	5	high
6	The company makes sure to monitor generated knowledge	3.922	0.907	6	high
general measure		4.344	0.565		high

As shown in table (8) the relative importance of the general mean of items on knowledge generation was high as the general mean was (4.344) with standard deviation (0.565). The item “The company makes sure to attract new knowledge through various means” ranked first with mean (4.653) and with high relative importance, while the item: “The company makes sure to monitor generated knowledge” ranked last with mean (3.922) and with high relative importance.

1- KNOWLEDGE STORAGE

Table (9): means, standard deviations and relative importance of knowledge storage items

No.	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Relative importance
1	The company has flexible mechanisms and tools to store available knowledge	3.718	0.973	7	high
2	The company has an organizational mechanism to index its available knowledge	4.065	0.920	3	high
3	The company keeps details and remarks concerning the available knowledge in a way that makes it easy to use	3.891	0.957	6	high
4	The company keeps paper records and documents to store data	4.367	0.851	1	high
5	The company invest modern technological means and computerized information systems in storing knowledge	4.017	0.868	4	high

6	The company documents experience, expertise and opinions provided by different parties by different means	3.986	0.826	5	high
7	The company motivate experienced employees as to ensure their preservation and continuity in their job	4.088	0.866	2	high
general measure		4.019	0.548		high

As shown in the above table, the relative importance of the general mean of items about knowledge storage is high as the general mean was (4.019)with standard deviation (0.548). The item “The company keeps paper records and documents to store data” ranked first with mean (4.367) and with high relative importance, whereas the item: “The company has flexible mechanisms and tools to store available knowledge”ranked last with mean (3.718) and with high relative importance.

2- KNOWLEDGE SHARING

Table (10): means, standard deviations and relative importance of knowledge sharing items

No.	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Relative importance
1	The company organizes workshops and activities of importance in exchanging implicit knowledge among its members	4.048	0.994	5	high
2	The company invest modern technological means in transferring knowledge among its employees	4.150	0.977	2	high
3	The company has policies and programs that would transfer knowledge between its various departments	4.058	0.938	4	high
4	The company provides various publications and documents to periodically disseminate knowledge to employees	4.133	0.931	3	high
5	The company seeks to implant the cultural of sharing among its employees	3.888	1.067	7	high
6	the company follows means, systems and policies that transfer knowledge to employees in a clear and comprehensible manner	4.020	0.931	6	high
7	The company facilitates communication between employees and between experts and specialists	4.303	0.744	1	high
general measure		4.086	0.615		high

As shown in the above table, the relative importance of the general mean of items about sharing knowledge is high as the general mean was (4.086)with standard deviation (0.615). The item “The company facilitates communication between employees and between experts and specialists” ranked first with mean (4.303) and with high relative importance, whereas the item: “The company seeks to implant the cultural of participation among its employees” ranked last with mean (3.888) and with high relative importance.

3- KNOWLEDGE APPLICATION

Table (11): means, standard deviations and relative importance of knowledge application items

No.	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Relative importance
1	relevant knowledge is provided to employees when needed in due time	4.374	0.755	1	high
2	the company provides means and tools necessary to apply the knowledge that is being shared in the best possible way	4.177	0.872	3	high
3	the company allows specialists and experienced persons to integrate their available knowledge in the production	4.214	0.915	2	high
4	the company applies emergency plans to resolve crisis and problems it faces	3.544	1.204	6	medium
5	The company tracks performance level and actual application of knowledge that has been shared with its employees	4.146	0.895	4	high
6	the company provides the appropriate environment for its employees to exchange feedback on knowledge added to them	3.694	1.046	5	high
general measure		4.025	0.624		high

As shown in the above table, the relative importance of the general mean of items about knowledge application is high as the general mean was (4.025) with standard deviation (0.624). The item “relevant knowledge is provided to employees when needed in due time” ranked first with mean (4.374) and with high relative importance, whereas the item: “the company applies emergency plans to resolve crisis and problems it faces” ranked last with mean (3.544) and with medium relative importance.

The following table compares between knowledge management processes as follows:

No.	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Relative importance
1	Knowledge generation	4.344	0.565	1	high
2	Knowledge storage	4.019	0.548	4	High
3	Knowledge sharing	4.086	0.615	2	high
4	Knowledge application	4.025	0.624	3	High
	knowledge management processes	4.118	0.515		high

The findings of table (12) indicates that the measure level of knowledge management processes in terms of the relative importance is high, where the mean was (4.118) with a standard deviation (0.515). The table also indicated that (knowledge generation) process ranked first with mean (4.344) and standard deviation (0.565) with high relative importance, while the (knowledge storage) process ranked last with mean (4.019), standard deviation (0.548) and with high relative importance.

PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL FUNCTION

Table (13): means, standard deviations and relative importance of items on performance appraisal function

No.	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Relative importance
1	The company has specialized and qualified staff to evaluate employees' performance	3.738	1.134	3	high
2	There are various standards to measure and evaluate employees performance	3.639	1.194	5	medium
3	Employees are evaluated as to meet the principles of justice through objective grounds	3.779	1.178	2	high
4	Employees are evaluated regularly and systematically	3.728	1.157	4	high
5	the evaluation system in industrial companies helps in determining weaknesses of employees	3.616	1.301	6	medium
6	The company makes sure that weaknesses of employees are addressed through the evaluation process	3.830	0.989	1	high
	general measure	3.721	0.680		high

As shown in the above table, the relative importance of the general mean of items concerning the function of performance appraisal is high as the general mean was (3.721) with standard deviation (0.680). The item “The company makes sure that weaknesses of employees are addressed through the evaluation process” ranked first with mean (3.830) and with high relative importance, while the item: “the evaluation system in industrial companies helps in determining weaknesses of employees” ranked last with mean (3.616) and with medium relative importance

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

In this part of the study, we review hypotheses testing as the main hypothesis and the hypotheses branching off from it have been subjected to multiple linear regression analysis. The results were as follows:

Test results of main hypothesis are

H0: there is no statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) for the knowledge management on the function of employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies.

Table (14): test results of the impact of all knowledge management processes on the employee performance appraisals

Dependent variable	Model Summary		ANOVA		Coefficient				
	R	R2	Calculate F	Sig F	statement	B	Stand ar d error	T	Sig t
Employee performance appraisal function	0.593	0.352	39.227	0.000	Knowledge generation	0.165	0.093	1.780	0.076
					Knowledge storage	0.188	0.092	2.051	0.041
					Knowledge sharing	0.209	0.085	2.466	0.014
					Knowledge application	0.217	0.078	2.768	0.006

*the impact is statistically significant at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$)

The results of table (14) indicates that the coefficient of determination (R = 0.593) refer to the relation between independent variables and the dependent variable. In addition, the impact of independent variables (knowledge management processes) on the dependent variable (employee performance appraisals) is statistically significant as the value of calculated F is (39.227) with Sig (0.000) which is less than 0.05. The value of coefficient of determination (R2= 0.352) indicating that (35.2%) of the variance in (employee performance appraisals) is explained through variances in all (knowledge management processes) together.

Table 14 reveals that the value of B in (knowledge generation) was (0.165) and the value of t is (1.780) with (Sig = 0.076) which indicates that the impact of this dimension is not significant. The value of B in(knowledge storage) process reached (0.188) and the value of t is (2.051) with (Sig = 0.041) which indicates that the impact of this dimension is significant. The value of B in (knowledge sharing) process reached (0.209) and the value of t is (2.466) with (Sig = 0.014)

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which indicates that the impact of this dimension is significant. The value of B in (knowledge application) process was (0.217) and the value of t is (2.768) with (Sig = 0.000) which indicates that the impact of this dimension is significant.

Based on the above, we reject the main hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that reads:

“There is a statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) for the knowledge management including its dimensions (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, knowledge application) on the function of employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies.”

The presence of significant impact of all knowledge management processes (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application) might be due to the importance of such processes in providing knowledge necessary for human resources management, in order to measure the results of the working individual's performance, through evaluating his ability to perform tasks assigned to him. In addition, to identify strengths and weaknesses, in order to take the appropriate procedure. On the other hand, the absence of significant impact of (knowledge generation) process, when studying the impact of all processes together, does not deny the importance of this process in evaluating performance. However, it appears that the impact of the rest of processes is considered more significant, especially that the performance appraisal process, though it relied on knowledge generation process, it is affected, at the end of the day, by what has been shared and applied of the previously stored knowledge.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study aimed at identifying the impact of knowledge management on the function of employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies, relying on the descriptive analytical approach. A questionnaire has been developed and distributed on individuals of the study sample consisting of managers of departments and sections of human resources in each company. The study reached a number of findings, most importantly, the presence of statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) for the knowledge management including its dimensions (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, knowledge application) on the function of employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies. The study has recommended that the Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies should follow an efficient evaluation system capable of identifying the employees' weaknesses.

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